

5G CITY

Grant Agreement No.761508 5GCITY/H2020-ICT-2016-2017/H2020-ICT-2016-2

D.1.1. Management Guidelines.

Dissemination Level	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
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Grant Agreement no: 761508	Project Acronym: 5G CITY	Project title: 5G CITY
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Lead Beneficiary: I2CAT	Document version: V1.0
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Work package: WP71 – Project Management

Deliverable title: D.1.1. Management Guidelines

Start date of the project: 01/06/2017 (duration 30 months)	Contractual delivery date: 31.08.2017	Actual delivery date: 31.08.2017
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Change History

Version	Date	Partners	Description/Comments
0.1	13-7-17	i2CAT	First draft by i2CAT
0.2	25-7-17	i2CAT	First review by i2CAT
0.3	4-8-17	I2CAT	Second draft by i2CAT
0.4	24-8-17	I2CAT	Second review by i2CAT
1.0	31-8-17	I2CAT	Final version by i2CAT
1.1	18-12-18	I2CAT	New version following EC review #1 recommendations for updates. Added: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clarification on the coordination between the Technical Manager and the Innovation Advisory Board (sec 1.20)

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarification on interdependencies of work packages and role of partners (Sec 1.3) • Update on Risk Management and table of risks
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5GCITY has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761508. The content of this deliverable does not reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Responsibility for the information and views expressed in the deliverable lies entirely with the author(s).

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Executive Summary

5GCITY is a complex project in terms of both, structure of the consortium and workflow between the beneficiaries. The project comprehends eighteen partners and includes universities, research centers, municipalities as well as public and private companies. In addition, the project forms part of the 5G PPP initiative which means that a dialogue is established with other projects and partners of the Public-Private Partnership.

This deliverable describes the strategy to implement an appropriate coordination framework, addressing general issues regarding the project structure, organization, partner responsibilities as well as specific guidelines about reporting, risk assessment and communication mechanisms.

The main points included in D1.1 are:

- Description of the project structure and of the documents of reference;
- Overall project status and progress monitoring of the work;
- Meetings, decision-making and conflict resolution procedures;
- Project reporting procedures including financial reporting;
- Initial Risk assessment;
- Editorial standards for project documents, contents and reports.

This deliverable is a handbook for the partners to have a common understanding of project procedures to efficiently implement it, achieving the objectives fixed in the Grant Agreement. It intends to complement the information already provided by the Grant agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

1. Project structure

1.1. Overview

The project management structure of 5GCITY aims to establish an effective framework to ensure the proper implementation of the action. This structure will help in the decision-making processes, the day-to-day management and the implementation of the work plan. The project structure is shown in Figure 1.

In short, the *General Assembly* is responsible for the highest level of monitoring and control of the project development. The *Project Coordinator (PC)*, assisted by the *Management Support Team (MST)*, will implement the decisions taken by the *General Assembly (GA)*, will be the single contact point with the EC and in charge of reporting duties. The *Technical Coordinator (TC)* will chair the *Technical Board (TB)*, composed by the *WP Leaders* and one representative from each beneficiary, and will be responsible for monitoring the development and implementation of the technical activity. Both, the Project Coordinator and the Technical Coordinator, will be the contact points with the 5GPPP. Last but not least, the *Innovation Board (IB)*, chaired by the *Innovation Manager (IM)*, will be composed by a senior representative with technical background of each partner and will monitor all the overall exploitation-related activities in the project. The current members of the different boards can be found in the confluence space of the project.

The Grant Agreement, the Consortium Agreement and the Collaboration Agreement with 5G PPP describe in detail the project management goals, the project management structure, and the contractual obligation of each part.

Figure 1-5GCITY Project Structure.

1.2. Organization and Roles

The roles of the Partners as well as the consortium government structures are defined in the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA). Below the main bodies (General Assembly, Technical Board and Innovation Board) that will coordinate the project are described, as well as the responsibilities of the different roles (Project Coordinator, Technical Manager, Innovation Manager, Management Support Team) that have been appointed.

General Assembly	Highest level of decision and project coordination committee.
Chaired by	The Project Coordinator (PC): Sergi Figuerola (i2CAT).
Participants	GA comprises one senior representative of each Partner, with the authority to commit their organizations to the decisions of the General Assembly.
Meeting frequency	Twice a year.
Attributions	<p>The role of the General Assembly is to ensure the follow-up of the project and to take the major decisions mainly on the following contractual aspects: (i) ECGA and CA amendment, (ii) termination of the contract and actions against underperforming partners, (iii) budget follow-up and transfers, (iv) set-up gender issues committee and monitor gender equality actions; and (v) conflict resolution. On the administrative control of the project, the GA has the day-to-day responsibility and organisation for the overall project progress (objectives, schedule, milestones, etc.), and approves project deliverables. The GA also ensures the Quality and the Risk Management aspects of the project.</p> <p>It is also noted that the non-technical WP6 responsible for the dissemination and exploitation of the project results, reports directly to the GA, and the GA takes any actions in case of a conflict.</p>

Technical Board & WP Leaders	Technical Board is the supervisory body for the technical execution of the Project
Chaired by	Technical Manager: Felipe Huici (NEC Laboratories) until 15-Oct-18. Gino Carrozzo (Nextworks) since then.
Participants	The TB is composed of the Work Package Leaders (WPLs) and the technical representatives (one from each partner) involved in the technical Work Packages.
Meeting frequency	General meetings each quarter.
Attributions	<p>The responsibilities of the WPLs is to plan, manage co-ordinate and follow-up the work within the work package; the WPL ensures the work is done in full accordance with the Description of Work and proposes proper actions when required. WPL has a part time managerial job combined with technical research work. They represent the WP interests and interfaces with other WPs through the TB meetings</p> <p>The Technical Board shall (i) prepare the meetings, propose decisions and prepare the agenda of the General Assembly according to Section 6.3.1.2 of the CA; (ii) seek a consensus among the Parties. (iii) be responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly, (iv) monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the Project, (v) collect information at least every 6 months on the progress of the Project, examine that information to assess the compliance of the Project with the Consortium Plan and, if necessary, propose modifications of the Consortium Plan to the General Assembly, (vi) agree on the Members of the Management Support Team, upon a proposal by the Coordinator, (vii) support the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the Funding Authority and in preparing related data and deliverables, (viii) prepare the content and timing of press releases and joint publications by the consortium or proposed by the Funding Authority in respect of the procedures of the Grant Agreement Article 29. (ix) In the case of abolished tasks as a result of a decision of the General Assembly, the Technical Board shall advise the General Assembly on ways to rearrange tasks and budgets of the Parties concerned. Such rearrangement shall take into consideration the legitimate commitments taken prior to the decisions, which cannot be cancelled.</p>

Innovation Board	The responsible body for innovation activities and the management of foreground and IPR during the project lifetime.
Chaired by	Innovation Manager (IM): Antonio Albanese (ITALTEL)
Participants	One representative of each Partner. Each Partner shall nominate a senior representative, with technical background, enabling to make consistent decisions around IPR and knowledge and innovation management to represent organization interests.
Meeting frequency	At least once a year.
Attributions	The role of the Innovation Board is to ensure that all the innovation activities within the project reach their target and maximize their impact. It is also in charge of studying and analysing both market and technical aspects, and bridging the project innovation achievements to a successful implementation and deployment in the real world. The IB ensures the management of foreground and IPR during the project lifetime, under the rules of the Consortium Agreement.

Project Coordinator	The Project Administrative Coordinator (PC) co-ordinates all the communication channels within all the partners to ensure progress and quality in the work and provides the Commission with technical, managerial and financial information.
Contact	Sergi Figuerola (i2CAT), sergi.figuerola@i2cat.net
Attributions	<p>The PC is Dr. Sergi Figuerola. The PC will act as the unique focal point for contacts and coordination with the European Commission; together with the Project Technical Manager (TM), and the Innovation Manager (IM), he will be a contact point with the other relevant ICT projects and external relationship with relevant bodies and other related activities.</p> <p>The Project Coordinator chairs the General Assembly. His major tasks are: (i) supervision of the overall project progress, (ii) preparation of the General Assembly, production of the minutes and follow-up of its decisions, (iii) Consortium Agreement coordination, (iv) collection of the audit certificates and supervision of distribution of EC's payments to partners, (v) preparation with the support of the TB of the reports, cost statements and project documents required by the EC, (vi) organisation of EC review meetings, (vii) supervision of IPR and knowledge management (with relevant advice from the IB), (viii) representative of the consortium to events, and (ix) coordination of the dissemination and communication activities</p> <p>The PC is also responsible to attend and follow activities of the Steering Board of the 5G-PPP. In detail, the PC will (i) attend Steering Board meetings; (ii) ensure the global consistency of the project with the programme; (iii) detect and address any risks in the project which may affect the programme; (iv) ensure sharing of information at the programme level; (v) perform self-assessment of the project towards achieving the programme KPIs; and (vi) any other request</p>

Management Support Team	The Management Support Team (MT) is composed by a team of employees familiar with administrative, legal, financial, communication and IPR issues who will support the Project Coordinator.
Contact	Jose Miguel Sanjuan (i2CAT), jose.miguel.sanjuan@i2cat.net

Attributions	<p>The Management Team (i) Assists the Project Coordinator in the project management tasks; (ii) Manages the delivery and the follow-up of administrative and financial documents (iii) Is a permanent contact point for the Coordinator and all the Partners regarding their participation in the project, responding to any relevant requests and maintaining a high level of communication within the Consortium.</p> <p>The MT is in charge of the day-to-day project management, and provides support and assistance to the different project bodies. In accordance with the EC requirements, it plays a hands-on role in administrative actions, including periodic reports, Certificates on Financial Statements, and communication on submission of Deliverables. The MT is responsible for ensuring that all of the administrative steps required for effective progress of the project will be fulfilled in good time.</p>
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Technical Manager	The project Technical Manager (TM) coordinates the activities of all partners in the project according to work plan.
Contact	Gino Carrozzo (Nextworks), g.carrozzo@nextworks.it from 15-Oct-2018
Attributions	<p>The TM will have the following responsibilities (i) chair of the TB; (ii) liaisons between the TB and the GA; (iii) technical relationship and coordination with other relevant R&D projects; (iv) supervision of the overall technical progress of the project; (v) consolidation of the technical reports; and (vi) follow-up and coordination of all technical work-packages.</p> <p>The TM is also responsible to attend, follow, and participate in the 5G-PPP Technical Board. In detail, the TM will (i) monitor the technical progress of the 5GCity project against the programme; (ii) consolidate technical requirements from the programme at the project level; (iii) ensure alignment of the project work towards technical work at programme level; (iv) discuss and design common demonstration frameworks (including the possibility to utilize the city distributed test-beds by other projects) between projects; and (v) to delegate appropriate actions at the working group level.</p> <p>The technical manager, along with the PC, will bridge the gap between the outputs of the project and the Innovation Board. In this sense the TM will use the QMRS for detecting innovation items that the WPL consider especially relevant and raising the attention of the IB about them. Making also sure that the partners receive the feedback from the IB.</p>

Innovation Manager	The Innovation Manager (IM) coordinates the activities of all partners around the IPR and knowledge management, and the feasible innovations.
Contact	Antonino Albanese (Italtel) , antonino.albanese@italtel.com
Attributions	<p>He will have the following responsibilities: (i) chair of the IB; (ii) liaisons between the IB and the GA; (iii) follow the standardization activities relevant to the project; (iv) consolidate the innovation reports; and (vi) follow-up all the innovation progress during the project lifetime (vii) monitoring all the overall exploitation-related activities in the project, according to the exploitation plan defined in the GA, putting emphasis on the overall exploitation impact of the project outcomes and its branding (viii) providing support to the partners in order to define the access rights and usage of their Background and project results (ix) advising the project with the right policies for protecting partners/project IPR, supporting the Coordinator on setting up an open innovation model that, according to Innovation goals of H2020, facilitates, from the coordination point of view, the generation of</p>

	innovation all along the project and strengthens the exploitation impact of the project results (x) providing advice on tools and mechanisms to improve the management, and (xi) following up all the innovation progress during the project lifetime.
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1.3. Overall Strategy of the Work Plan and interdependencies

5GCity Consortium will follow agile-based methodologies for all the technical activities within the project. This allows to have an incremental development and progress towards the achievement of the objectives maximising the collaboration among partners, the inter-workpackage activities, the deployment and assessment in city pilots.

As per DoA, the work is divided into six work packages, as illustrated in Figure 2, which target the implementation of three innovation pillars, i.e. 5GCity MEC node platform and network virtualization, orchestration, SDK and service programming models, and city-wide use cases implementation and validation.

Figure 2-5GCITY Project workpackages.

The workplan is structured to evolve in three major iterations, driven by milestones MS7 (M12), MS8 (M18) and MS9 (M28), that will drive the interim releases for the technical development work packages, to be performed at M12, M18, and M28.

All partners participate to WP2 to develop the 5GCity architecture. A key role in Business Model development is covered by the Operators (Wind Tre, Cellnex) and technology providers (Italtel also as innovation manager and WP2 leader, i2CAT, Nextworks, VOSYS, Acceleran, ADLINK, Ubiwhere) and verticals (RAI, BTVE, MOG).

WP3 team works on virtualization of resource-constrained devices, network resources, and specific lightweight VNF data modelling for MEC nodes. Key partners in this activity cluster are VOSYS (also WP leader), NEC, i2CAT, Nextworks.

WP4 is focused on the design and development of the 5GCity orchestrator, the SDK and associated service programming models and the distributed machine-learning solution. Key partners in this activity cluster are i2CAT (also WP leader), Nextworks, Italtel, Ubiwhere, Univ. Bristol, NEC.

WP5 works on the verification, integration, and deployment of the 5GCity components over the city-wide infrastructures, and on the use case activities related to the neutral host and media vertical scenarios. Key partners in their workpackage are Univ. Bristol, IMI Barcelona, Comune di Lucca for the city infrastructures and some use cases, NEC, Nextworks, i2CAT, Acceleran, RAI, WindTre, Italtel, BTVE, MOG and Ubiwhere for the use cases.

All the partners are involved in WP6 for impact generation in terms of communication and dissemination activities, individual and joint exploitations, participation and potential contributions to standards and open source initiatives.

The interdependencies among the different work packages are aligned to the three project's research & innovation pillars as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3 -5GCity PERT Diagram.

The bold tick lines in Figure 3 identify the major results transferred from one workpackage to the other. Dotted lines represent feedback reporting from technical workpackages (implementation and assessment) to design activities in WP2 to update specifications based on actual implementation experiences.

Key to the successful execution of the workplan is the collaborations and commitment of each and every partner towards joint collaborative innovation activities, under the supervision and guidance of the Technical Board.

1.4. Reference Documents

There are three documents that define the rights and obligations that apply to the entities involved in the project: The Grant Agreement defines the contractual obligations with the EC, the Consortium Agreement is an internal agreement between the consortium members and the Collaboration Agreement of the Consortium with 5G PPP addresses the relationship with this entity.

1.4.1. Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement (ECGA) sets out the rights and obligations and the terms and conditions applicable to the grant awarded to the beneficiaries for implementing the action. Is signed by the EC and the beneficiaries of the action. It has seven parts:

- Terms and Conditions

- Annex 1 Description of the action (DOA)
- Annex 2 Estimated budget for the action & Additional information on the estimated budget
- Annex 3 Accession Forms
- Annex 4 Model for the financial statements
- Annex 5 Model for the certificate on the financial statements (CFS)
- Annex 6 Model for the certificate on the methodology

Any modification of the Grant Agreement must be approved by the General Assembly, the EC and implemented through an amendment of the document. The latest version of the document will be uploaded in the Participant Portal and in confluence.

1.4.2. Consortium Agreement

The purpose of the Consortium Agreement (CA) is to specify with respect to 5GCITY the relationship among the Parties, in particular concerning the organisation of the work between the Parties, the management of the Project and the rights and obligations of the Parties concerning inter alia liability, Access Rights and dispute resolution. The CA is based in an adaptation of the DESCA 1.2 model.

Any modification of the Grant Agreement must be approved by the General Assembly and implemented through an amendment of the document. The latest version of the document can be found in the confluence.

1.4.3. 5G PPP Collaboration Agreement

5GCITY has been funded under the 5G-PPP Phase 2 and is considered a 5G-PPP complementary grant agreement, in the context of Article 41.4 of the Annotated Model Grant Agreement for H20202 and therefore, *must provision for the appropriate joint actions, 5G Global Events, Work Groups, KPIs progress evaluation and the grant of additional access rights by joining such a collaboration agreement (...)* Beneficiaries who are already parties to this agreement do not need to sign it again.

The latest version of the document can be found in the confluence.

1.4.4. Additional documentation

In order to facilitate the management of the project additional information covering financial management, administrative management, dissemination guidelines etc. will be regularly uploaded in the management section of the confluence.

2. Project collaborative platform and Email Communication

The infrastructure chosen to hold the documentation produced by the project (deliverables, agendas, action points, presentations...) is the Confluence solution by Atlassian that is used as project collaborative platform of the project.

<https://confluence.i2cat.net/display/5GCITY/5GCity+Home>

The Project Coordinator and the Technical and Innovation Manager will be the ultimate responsible for maintaining with coherence the contents, organization and availability to the partners. The platform has the following sections:

➤ 5G PPP WGS: Information related with the working groups of the 5G PPP: member of the boards, minutes of the meetings, etc.
➤ Contacts: updated list of the contacts
➤ Management
○ F2F meetings Minutes, agendas, presentations and logistic indications (accommodation, maps and indications) regarding the meetings.
○ Conference Calls. Summary of each conference call including attendees, discussion items and actions points.
○ Innovation Management: page of the innovation board.
○ Continuous Reporting: This section will be used to gather the information of the Six-Month Interim reports (technical + financial status updates) and the Quarterly Management reports (only technical) between semester reports. It will include the definitive version of the Periodic and Final Reports.
➤ Templates & Logos: Templates of deliverables, presentations, posters and the official logos of the project and the partners.
○ Dissemination Material: leaflets, presentations, video clips and other outreach material. The section will also include the press releases generated by the project.
○ Papers and presentations: Scientific outputs.

Figure 4-Structure of Confluence.

The email communication reflector of the project will be hosted by the Coordinator, i2CAT who established and maintains the following email lists:

5GCITY-GA	GA members	5gcity-ga@i2cat.net
5GCITY-TECHNICAL	Technical Board members	5gcity-technical@i2cat.net
5GCITY-ADMIN	Legal, contractual and financial issues	5gcity-admin@i2cat.net
5GCITY-WP1	WP1 Project Management issues	5gcity-wp1@i2cat.net
5GCITY-WP2	WP2 5GCITY Architecture, Requirements, & Use Cases	5gcity-wp2@i2cat.net
5GCITY-WP3	WP3 5GCITY Virtualisation	5gcity-wp3@i2cat.net
5GCITY-WP4	WP4 5GCITY Orchestrator and service programming	5gcity-wp4@i2cat.net

5GCITY-WP5	WP5 5GCITY Vertical scenarios & city-wide pilots	5gcity-wp5@i2cat.net
5GCITY-WP6	WP6 5GCITY Dissemination, standardization & exploitation	5gcity-wp6@i2cat.net

Table 1-List of mail reflectors

All emails sent to the reflector will include the following text in brackets in the subject [5GCITY-all], [5GCITY-WPX] etc.

The purpose of this set of emails is to exchange information between the different boards, groups, WP that compose the project.

In case a new member joins the project, an email with the specific request should be sent to the MT who will include it in the corresponding section.

2.1. Conference-Call Collaboration

For virtual meetings a dedicated conference bridge (WebEx video conference tool provided by Cisco and hosted by i2CAT) will be provided by i2CAT. All details regarding the access to the bridge will be provided by i2CAT technical team and will be stored in the confluence.

Additional ad-hoc conference calls should be regulated by the following general rules:

- The partners will schedule the date of the conference, using also appropriate support tools. (e.g., doodle).
- An invitation to the project email list with the exact time, agenda and information on how to join the conference call will be circulated, at least one day before the conference call.
- i2CAT technical team will manage the conference platform and inform the consortium how to login to that conference system.

2.2. Meetings

Meetings can be either face to face or virtual meetings. For each meeting the following documentation will be produced and uploaded on the respective folder in the document repository of confluence

- **Notifications:** All formal face to face meetings (GA, TB, etc.) will be notified at least three weeks in advance. Virtual meetings will be notified at soon as possible.
- **Documentation:** Agenda, proposed resolutions, decisions and supporting documentation will be available to all attendees at least one week before the face to face meeting. In virtual meeting's agenda and discussions points will be shared as soon as possible through confluence.
- **Minutes:** Meeting minutes of all meetings (F2F or online) will be formally reported. The chairperson shall produce written minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. In face to face meetings he/she shall send the draft minutes to all members within 10 calendar days of the meeting. In virtual meetings the minutes will be uploaded in confluence within one week of the meeting.

The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from sending or uploading no member has sent an objection in writing to the chairperson with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes.

The accepted minutes will be accessible from the documents repository in the confluence and are the document that's binds the decisions taken by the different bodies.

- Face to face minutes will have to include a list of participants on each day of the meeting. Virtual meetings minutes will have to include a list of the participants attending to the call.

2.3. Hosting a face to face meeting

Throughout the project lifetime, members may host project meetings.

- It is advisable that the location is reachable to avoid extra costs. The host has to provide logistic information on how to reach the venue of the meeting.
- The costs of hosting the meeting will be covered by the hosting partner and the travel costs will be covered by each participant.
- The host must provide: Meeting rooms with audio-visual equipment necessary for the presentations and network connectivity.
- It is also recommended (general practice although not obligatory) to provide Water, coffee breaks and lunch and to organize one social event (e.g., invite partners for one evening meal).

2.4. Voting rules

In the event that is needed to vote a decision, each body has to take into consideration the quorum. As stated in the CA each Consortium Body shall not deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its Members are present or represented (quorum). If the quorum is not reached, the chairperson of the Consortium Body shall convene another ordinary meeting within 15 calendar days. If in this meeting the quorum is not reached once more, the chairperson shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide even if less than the quorum of Members is present or represented, unless a major decision is taken (section 6.3.1.2 of the CA).

Each Member of a Consortium Body present or represented in the meeting shall have one vote. The Coordinator shall have double vote in case of a tie.

Each body has his own voting rules:

- Decisions of the **General Assembly** shall be taken by a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast
- Decisions of the **Technical Board** shall be taken by consensus whenever possible. No voting will occur within the Technical Board. In case of conflict or for decisions beyond Work Packages responsibilities, the Work Package leader shall prepare a description of the problem and its possible solution and the Technical Manager shall refer to the General Assembly.
- Decisions of the **Innovation Board** will be taken by consensus whenever possible. No voting will occur within the Innovation Board. In case of conflict or for decisions beyond its responsibilities, the Innovation Board will refer to the General Assembly.

A Member which can show that its own work, time for performance, costs, liabilities, intellectual property rights or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a decision of a Consortium Body may exercise a **veto** with respect to the corresponding decision or relevant part of the decision. How to apply the veto is specified in 6.2.4 of the CA.

3. Project Reporting

3.1. General rules

The following general rules will be followed for all the outputs of the project:

Language: English is the official language in 5GCITY. In consequence all relevant documents and written communications will be written in English. The only exception is related with the dissemination materials, such as press releases or technical publications, which can be translated to other languages. In this scenario, each partner is responsible for translation of official 5GCITY documents to its language of interest.

Responsibility: Each partner is responsible for the quality of their contribution and should provide the information to fulfil any requirement to complete a deliverable, milestone or report. The editor of the document is responsible for the overall quality of the work, including: requesting and collecting contributions, and integrating them in the different releases. Overall scientific coordination is responsibility of WP leaders, TM and the Coordinator

The PC will provide templates to ensure a homogenous output of all project documents. It is mandatory for all partners to follow the project templates. When needed each template will provide a style guide for assuring a coherent output.

3.2. Events that must be immediately reported

The Partners must inform immediately the PC, who will inform the PO and the Consortium, of any events which are likely to affect significantly or delay the implementation of the action or the EU's financial interests:

- Change of the PI or LEAR.
- Changes in its legal, financial, technical, organizational or ownership situation or those of its linked third parties and
- Changes in the name, address, legal form, organization type of its linked third parties;
- Any circumstance affecting the de decision to award the grant or compliance with the requirements under the agreement.

In addition, each beneficiary must keep information stored in the Participant Portal Beneficiary Register up to date, in particular, its name, address, legal representatives, legal form and organization type.

3.3. Project reporting calendar

The list of official commitments is summarized in table 2.

Month	Month (ii)	Events
1	Jun-17	
2	Jul-17	Milest.12 Dissemination environment available (NEC)
3	Aug-17	D1.1 Management Guidelines (I2CAT)
4	Sept-17	Milest.3 First architecture w.r.t. and requirements available (ITL)
5	Oct-17	
6	Nov-17	D1.2 Project Innovation Strategy and DMP (I2CAT)

	Nov-17	D6.1 Project Dissemination and Communication Plan (I2CAT)
7	Dec-17	1st SPR (months 1-6)
	Dec-17	D2.1 5GCity System Requirements and Use Cases (COMUNE DI LUCCA)
8	ene.-18	
9	Feb-18	D6.2 Standardization and Exploitation Plan (NEC)
9	Feb-18	Milest.13 First 5GCity newsletter ready (NEC)
10	Mar-18	
11	Jan-18	
12	May-18	
	May-18	D2.2 5GCity Architecture & Interfaces Definition (ITL)
	May-18	D3.1 5GCity Edge Virtualization Infrastructure Design (VOSYS)
	May-18	D4.1 Orchestrator Design, Service programming, and Machine-learning Models (I2CAT)
	May-18	D5.1 1 5GCity Infrastructure Design and Definition (UNIVBRIS)
	May-18	D6.3 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Standardization Activities M12 (NXW)
	May-18	Milest.6 Prototypes design and first iteration available (VOSYS)
	May-18	Milest.9 5GCity infrastructure design finalized (UNIVBRIS)
13	Jun-18	End 1sts period
	Jun-18	2nd SPR (months 7-13))
	Jun-18	D1.3 First Periodic Report (I2CAT)
	Jun-18	Milest.1 First periodic review (I2CAT)
14	Jul-18	Submission of PR
15	Aug-18	
16	Sept-18	Project Review (to be confirmed)
17	Oct-18	
18	Nov-18	D1.4 Intermediate Quality Report (I2CAT)
	Nov-18	Milest.7 Intermediate prototypes (VOSYS)
	Nov-18	Milest.10 Intermediate prototypes deployed in the city-wide infrastructure (UNIVBRIS)
19	Dec-18	3rd Internal report (14-18)
	Dec-18	D2.3 5GCity Architecture, and Interfaces Update (ITL)
	Dec-18	Milest.4 Architecture updated upon feedback received (ITL)
20	ene.-19	
21	Feb-19	
22	Mar-19	4 th Internal Report (19-21)- QMR
23	Jan-19	
24	May-19	D3.2 5GCity Virtualization Infrastructure Interim Release (NEC)
	May-19	D4.2 Scalable Orchestrator Interim Release (I2CAT)
	May-19	D5.2 Validation and Integration of the Developed Modules and Solutions (UNIVBRIS)
	May-19	D6.4 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Standardization Activities M24 (I2CAT)
	May-19	Milest.11 Prototypes deployed in the city-wide infrastructure (UNIVBRIS)
25	Jun-19	5 th Internal Report (22-24) -QMR
	Jun-19	D2.4 5GCity Final Architecture, and Interfaces (I2CAT)
	Jun-19	Milest.5 Final architecture and interfaces release (ITL)
26	Jul-19	
27	Aug-19	
28	Sept-19	6 th Internal Report (25-27)-QMR
	Sept-19	D3.3 5GCity Virtualization Infrastructure Implementation (VOSYS)

	Sept-19	D4.3 Location-aware Machine Learning Mechanisms (NEC)
	Sept-19	D4.4 Final 5GCity Orchestrator Release (I2CAT)
	Sept-19	Milest.8 Final prototype available (VOSYS)
29	Oct-19	
30	Nov-19	End Project / 5 SPR (25-30)
	Nov-19	D1.5 Second Periodic Report (I2CAT)
	Nov-19	D1.6 Final Project Report (I2CAT)
	Nov-19	D2.5 5GCity Business models, and techno-economics evaluation (INCITES)
	Nov-19	D5.3 City-wide Pilot Validation City-wide (IMI BCN)
	Nov-19	D6.5 Final Report on Dissemination, Exploitation, and Standardization Activities (NEC)
	Nov-19	Milest.2 Second periodic review (I2CAT)
	Nov-19	Milest.14 Five journal published, one workshop organized and one public event pilot demo (NEC)

Table 2- Project Schedule

3.4. Deliverables

This section describes the deliverables that ought to be submitted during the project as stated in the DOA. Deliverables must be submitted in due time (end of the month indicated in the DoA).

The deliverables are the main output of the project and can be either labelled as *Report* or as *Demonstrator*. In either case a report following the template proposed in Annex-1 must be followed. The definitive version of the deliverables will be submitted to the Participant Portal and uploaded to confluence by the PC.

The dissemination level can be Public or Confidential (EC and members of the Consortium). In the case of public deliverables, once have been submitted to the EC the definitive content will be shared internally with the Consortium through confluence. If there are not written objections, public deliverables will be uploaded to the project webpage once are approved by the EC. Public deliverables will be published by the EC immediately in Cordis once have been approved.

3.4.1. Deliverable Acceptance Process

A clear quality process will be applied for the final acceptance of a deliverable. The responsibilities in the consortium are the following ones:

- The **WPL** and **TM** are responsible for fostering the discussions well in advance so the **Editor** can propose a TOC at least 180 days before the deadline.
- The **Editor** for each deliverable will be appointed by the **lead partner** of the deliverable. He will propose to the rest of the consortium a distribution of the tasks and it will verify the contents of the documents assuring that the information contained is relevant and of importance to the research work and activity carried out in a given project task.
- The **Reviewer(s)** will make revision of the deliverable and assess if some modifications or conflict resolution would be needed. The **reviewer** will assure the conformity of the document with the quality criteria and also act as interface to **the Editor**.
- To comply with article 8.4.1 of the CA the editor will send to the consortium at least 20 days before the submission, the final draft of the deliverable.
- The final submission of the deliverable will be made by the **PC**.

The internal schedule for deliverables is summarized below:

Action	Days to deadline	Responsible	Receiver
TOC, section assignment to partners,	180 days	Lead beneficiary (editor).	Partners involved+WPL involved+TM
First consolidated draft of the deliverable + initial feedback from editor	90 days.	Lead beneficiary (editor).	Partners involved+WPL involved+TM
Second consolidated draft of the deliverable	60 days.	Lead beneficiary (editor).	Partners involved+WPL involved+TM
Final draft (ready to be send to reviewers)	30 days	Lead beneficiary (editor).	Partners involved+WPL involved+TM
Reviewers feedback	15 days.	Reviewers.	Editor.
Revised inputs	10 days.	All authors.	Editor.
Final consolidated draft	4 days.	Editor.	PC.

Table 3- Deliverable review work-flow.

3.4.2. Quality criteria

The **editor** and the **reviewer** must take into account the following quality criteria against which every single deliverable will be evaluated:

- The deliverable must address all aspects related to the **purpose and scope** for which the related research activity is carried out. Each deliverable should provide information according to the scope of the specific research work and should be focused on the key aspects of the deliverable scope.
- Each deliverable should have a **coherent depth of information** with respect to the deliverable scope, purpose and type of research activity described. The deliverable must include an executive summary and proper conclusions if necessary. The contribution of each partner involved should be correctly reported.
- The **impact** of the deliverable and any progress beyond the state-of-the-art has to be clearly identified, and any expected output (paper, patents, standard...) included. All background information used in the documents should be linked to appropriate references. Foreground information and results, should be clearly described and should be technically supported in order to avoid any misinterpretation or misunderstanding.
- All the documents must follow the style guidelines to provide a **uniform appearance and structure**. A clear and correct language has to be used, appropriate abbreviations and references have to be included and listed and a logical order followed.

3.5. Milestones

Milestones will be marked as *achieved* by the PC in the Participant Portal. At least with two days in advance of the deadline the lead beneficiary of the milestone will send the PC and the TB a short paragraph explaining the arguments that support having achieved the milestone. In case that is necessary the Lead Beneficiary will provide as support the necessary documents or reports that will be keep by the PC.

3.6. Internal reporting

In order to follow-up the effort of the partners each six months the partners will be asked to fill-in through confluence, a Semester Progress Report (SPR) of tasks, effort and the expenses executed during the previous six months. The internal reporting will be in months 7, 13, 19, 25,30.

SMR	Covering	Deadline
SPR1	Month 1-6	20-12-17
SPR2	Month 7-13	10-7-17
SPR3	Month 13-18	20-12-18
SPR4	Month 19-24	10-6-19
SPR5	Month 25-30	20-12-19

Table 4- Deadline Internal Reporting

The Semester Progress Report (SPR) includes of the following parts:

1. Work Package Report: To be completed by the WPL and must include a textual reporting of the work progress and achievements during the period per Work Package. **Contributions must be done in plain text avoiding when possible bullets. This text will be used in the corresponding Periodic Report.**
2. Individual Report: To be completed by each partner. It must include
 - Short description of the activity: main actions and achievements and also deviation from DoA and/or failure to achieve a planned objective. **Contributions must be done in plain text avoiding when possible bullets. This text will be used in the corresponding Periodic Report**
 - List of dissemination activities during the period.
 - PM's expended by partner per WP during the reporting period.
 - Financial Reporting: In this part each beneficiary will have to report the specific cost incurred during the reporting period by cost categories.
 - Any foreseen deviation of the effort, the costs or the deadlines.

The Project Coordinator will keep the EC Project Officer informed about changes, problems, and deviations from the work plan or the budget.

3.7. Periodic Reporting

The Periodic Reporting is submitted through the Participant Portal by the PC. There are two Periodic Reports, first one covering the activity and costs of months 1 to 13 (submission 30-7-18)¹, second one covering months 14 to 30 (submission 30-1-20). Along with the second Periodic Report a Final Report will be submitted. Details on this report will be provided in advance.

The periodic reporting has two main parts (i) the Periodic Technical report which contains a progress report detailing the activity in the period reported and the financial statements that declare the expenses during the period. Submitting these reports is a contractual obligation with the EC.²

¹ Official deadline 30-8-18, but as informed in the KOM the internal deadline is 30-7-18 to avoid delays due to the holidays.

² An extended explanation of each item that covers the reporting can be find [here](#). This section is a summary of the information provided by the EC.

3.7.1. The Periodic Technical report

The periodic technical report is sub-divided in 2 parts:

PART A to be filled in on-line into the SYGMA system, it is composed by the following forms:

1. **Publishable summary** – This is stand-alone document that must be written in a language easily understandable by broader public.
2. **Deliverables:** All deliverables foreseen for the reporting period must be included. If any deliverable has been delayed the new release date must be included.
3. **Milestones:** All milestones foreseen for the reporting period must be included. If any milestone has been delayed the new release date must be included.
4. **Critical implementation risks and mitigation actions:** At the end of each period beneficiaries should give the state of play of every risk identified in Annex 1 and, if necessary, give new mitigation measures.
5. **Publications:** detailed list of the publication related with the project. For reporting the publications, a DOI is mandatory.
6. **Dissemination and exploitation of results:** Scientific publications and Dissemination and communication activities specifying (i) total funding amount (ii) the number of Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the project by category, (iii) the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of all dissemination and communication activities.
7. **Patents**
8. **Innovation:** Any prototypes, new products launched to the market, innovations introduced in private companies.
9. **Impact on SME:** evolution of turnover and employees of the SMEs
10. **Gender:** information about the number of women involved in the project.

PART B: Is a detailed narrative report of the activities carried out by the consortium during the reporting period. This document has to be completed and uploaded by the PC, and includes the following parts:

1. Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and overview of the progress. Any deviation has to be justified.
 - 1.1. Objectives. List of objectives and the work carried out to fulfil them
 - 1.2. Explanation of the work carried per WP detailing the contribution of each beneficiary
 - 1.3. Impact. Summary of objectives achieved as defined in section 2 of the DoA
2. Update of the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results.
3. Update of the data management plan.
4. Follow-up of recommendations and comments from previous review(s)
5. Deviations from Annex 1
 - 5.1. Tasks: Provide details on the status of the tasks including those not fully implemented, deliverables not submitted or objectives not achieved.
 - 5.2. Use of resources: Explanation on how the financial resources have been used.

3.7.2. Individual Financial Report

At the end of Period 1 (M1-M13) and Period 2 (M14-M30), each partner will provide the Financial Statements (FS) to the coordinator. The FS will include the costs of the period and will be declared in order to claim reimbursement to the European Commission. The FS will be complemented with an audit certificate when accumulated funding surpasses 325.000 €.

The following rules must be specially taken into account when addressing the financial report.³ Each partner:

³ Please refer to Article 6 of the [AMGA](#) for full explanation.

1. Shall be solely responsible for **justifying its own costs**, (not the EC contribution) that must be (i) Linked with the project (ii) Incurred by the beneficiary. (iii) Incurred during the duration of the Project. (iv) According to usual practices of the beneficiary. (v) Reasonable and justified. (vi) Identifiable and verifiable
2. **Can only report eligible direct costs:** Those costs that are specifically incurred because of carrying out an action (personnel, travel, equipment, consumables, minor tasks, other...). Indirect Costs (overheads) is a Flat Rate of 25%. Non-Eligible costs cannot be reported (Dividends, Interests, provisions, debts, Exchange losses, bank Commissions, excessive costs, deductible VAT, etc.)
3. The beneficiaries must declare costs based on the **actual amounts spent:** Personnel Costs based on actual staff costs (See article 6.2.A of the ECGA for more information on how to calculate personnel cost). Other direct costs based on actual costs for the project. Depreciation costs for assets. Real costs of consumables

4. Risk management

The risk management plan identifies the threats to the project, their risk and the measure to mitigate these risks. The PC will evaluate the risks with the information in each SPR. The table below summarizes the risks identified during the proposal phase.

Number	Description	Risk Mitigation Measures
1	Partner problems (e.g. underperforming partner; a key partner leaves the project; disagreement between partners)	WP leaders monitor progress (including potential partner conflicts) at WP level and communicate difficulties to the Project Co-ordinator. The consortium agreement will ultimately provide a framework for underperforming partners and conflict resolution procedures. The consortium is of sufficient strength and diversity for partners to replace if required. Reassignment of responsibilities to other partners or inclusion of new partners if required.
2	Expertise risks (e.g. a key person with a specific expertise leaves the project)	Proper documentation through project reporting and deliverables can mitigate this risk, although depending on the profile and the moment of the project, work may need to be rescheduled in order to bring a new person up to speed. Clear communication channels in the project will allow partners inform the coordinator promptly of this risk
3	Project execution risks (e.g. milestones or critical deliverables are delayed)	The project will continuously carry out technological (and business) watch as part of the different on-going design activities, in order to reduce this risk. The TM, assessed by the IM, will be responsible to continuously monitor technological landscape trends related to 5GCity. Furthermore, the Project will emphasize the interaction with the open-source community, anticipating also joint efforts.
4	Technological risks (e.g. key technologies are not available at the expected time, there is a disruptive change in technology and/or business, substantial open-source components change, or upstreaming issues)	The project will continuously carry out technological (and business) watch as part of the different on-going design activities, in order to reduce this risk. The TM, assessed by the IM, will be responsible to continuously monitor technological landscape trends related to 5GCity. Furthermore, the Project will emphasize the interaction with the open-source community, anticipating also joint efforts.
5	Project objectives lose relevance	The TB and the IB periodically will review the progress in the Edge, and Cloud computing fields, virtualization, and 5G trends. If required, the consortium may agree minor changes in the work plan, under the final agreement of the GA.

6	Similar solution (i.e. a similar solution is announced to the market during the project lifetime)	Adopting agile approach will allow the consortium to disseminate and exploit full functioning, even if not complete version of 5GCity solution, in order to not loose competitive advantage. Moreover, the analysis of the appearing best solutions will give the opportunity to improve 5GCity results.
7	Single module does not achieve the expected quality (e.g. lower TRL, or malfunction of one module)	All the components for the components are expected to achieve a reasonably high TRL, from the research perspective, as they might be based on already existing technologies. However, there exists the risk that any of the modules does not meet the expected quality. Again, an agile-based methodology enables the project technical and innovation boards to rapidly identify such a risk in case it happens and to take effective mitigation actions to solve the issue.
8	City-wide deployment cannot be performed (e.g. change of location, natural disaster)	There exists a risk for the city-wide use case deployments, since 5GCity will have real deployments, in case that the locations selected cannot be utilized for the deployments in WP5. In order to mitigate this risk, the consortium will periodically assess the risk with the involved cities, and plans to have a background solution (i.e. selection of a different location) in case there is the need to do that to ensure the success of the deployments.
9	Expected KPIs for the objectives cannot be met (e.g. size of the unikernels cannot be reduced at the same time they are operational)	There is a common risk for the technical work package in case they are not able to meet the expected KPIs (refer to Section 1). In order to avoid this risk, the PC and the TM will periodically assess the status of the developments in order to evaluate if there exists the need to update any of the KPIs, under agreement of the GA.

Table 5- List of risks

So far, the following actions have been implemented to mitigate the identified risks

Risk 1. Partner problems. The Consortium has established a CA to address any possible conflict and the Management Guidelines (D1.1) will be shared with the partners in order to facilitate the understanding of the project structure and the contractual obligation. Each two weeks a Regular Plenary call (comprehending all the partners) have been appointed to monitor the evolution of the technical work. Additionally, a six-month monitoring has been established to control the evolution the effort. Face to face meetings will be done three times a year.

Risk 2. Expertise risks: a proper documentation system has been settled and clear communication channels introduced. Any deviation from a partner will be analysed by the PC in a case by case basis.

Risk 3, 4, 5 and 6 Project execution risks, technological risks, loss of relevance or similar solution: The mitigation of this risks is related with a technological watch that is being done by the members of the TB.

Risk 7, 8 and 9. These risks are related with further developments of the work and in consequence no mitigation procedures have been implemented so far.

Update December 2018. Following to the project review the EC requested an update of the critical risks. Table 6 includes an update for risks 1, 3, 6 and 9. It also identifies a more specific risks (#10) and its mitigation measures.

#	Description of risk	WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	Did you apply risk mitigation measures?	Did your risk materialise?	Comments
1	Partner problems (e.g. underperforming partner; a key partner leaves the project; disagreement between partners)	WP1	The Project Management Board (TM+WP leaders) continuously monitor progress (including potential partner conflicts) at WP level and communicate difficulties to the Project Coordinator. The consortium agreement ultimately provides a framework for underperforming partners and conflict resolution procedures. The consortium is of sufficient strength and diversity for partners to replace if required. Reassignment of responsibilities to other partners or inclusion of new partners if required.	Partly during PR1	Yes, during PR1	Bristol is Open (BIO), third party of Univ. Bristol withdraw from the project as on 31.03.2018, due to changes in their strategic direction. Following extensive assessments, the Univ. Bristol has since taken responsibility of the associated work and will provide access to services, equivalent to the ones provided by BIO, so that the project meets its objectives.
3	Project execution risks (e.g. milestones or critical deliverables are delayed)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	This risk is reduced by the expertise of partners (both tech. and mgt.) that will allow rapid identification of planning drifts. Work package roadmaps and periodic updates among partners and within the PMB are key management elements for this mitigating this risk. This allows to correctly plan the resources devoted to the fulfilment of the target objective/deadline. In	YES	PARTLY	During PR1 the consortium decided to postpone of 20 working days the release of D5.1 to improve its quality and impact. The delay did not propagate to other WP5 activities

			case the contents of milestones or deliverables at a given date remain still not satisfactory after the internal process of reviews, the PMB can decide for a short 15-20 days delay to improve contents and value proposed, only under the assumption that the subsequent activities depending on the milestone or the deliverable remain manageable and delay is not further increased.			
6	Similar solution is announced to the market during the project lifetime	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	Adopting agile approach will allow the consortium to disseminate and exploit full functioning, even if not complete version of 5GCity solution, in order to not loose competitive advantage. Moreover, the analysis of the appearing best solutions will give the opportunity to improve 5GCity results. The partners involved in the IB and on business model definition will carefully monitor the market and the 5GCity value proposition and innovation.	NO	NO	The partners involved in the IB and on business model definition will carefully monitor the market and the 5GCity value proposition and innovation.
9	Expected KPIs for the objectives cannot be met (e.g. size of the unikernels cannot be reduced at the same time they are operational)	WP3, WP4, WP5	There is a common risk for the technical work package in case they are not able to meet the expected KPIs (refer to Section 1). In order to avoid this risk, the PC and the TM will periodically assess the status of the developments in order to evaluate if there exists the need to update any of the KPIs, under agreement of the GA. Moreover, 5GCity KPIs will be defined along with measurement methodologies, and cross-checked with SDO related activities and other 5G PPP project	NO	NO	The 5GCity TM is part of the ad-hoc team on KPI definition withing the 5G PPP Technical Board. This action guarantees a continuous alignment with the 5G PPP programme actions related to KPIs

			experiences to base the project assessment on solid background and a common			
10	Developed Use Cases do not properly show the value of 5G and 5GCity platform	WP5	<p>The Consortium has selected a widely accepted set of media use cases to validate the project solutions. Many projects and industries (some part of the Consortium) just do execute research in this field granting a valuable background to be used for reference and benchmarking.</p> <p>Nevertheless, there exist a risk that the applications developed in the various 5GCity use cases do not properly show and assess the benefits of 5G in general and the 5GCity platform solution in particular. This risk might appear during the first phase of the project, when the development of use cases and 5GCity platform proceed in parallel as per workplan. However, the risk is minimised on an entire project lifespan thanks to a detailed planning of 5GCity platform roll-out activities in the three city pilots, accompanied by basic network performance testing, and the subsequent integration of the platform with the use case applications to test application-level KPIs.</p> <p>The Consortium has expertise to manage these activities and achieve the objectives set, and the workplan is structured in a way to properly implement the integration activities after all the preparatory phases of WP3, WP4 and WP5 have been completed.</p>	NO	NO	Developments of use cases and platform components until PR1 may appear loosely coupled to 5GCity platform. Actually, PR1 status is a snapshot of intermediate preparatory activities on use cases and 5GCity platform component developments, which are planned to be integrated by M2

Table 6.Update table of project risks

5. Dissemination

Dissemination of the project outputs to society is one of the objectives included in the H2020 program. Dissemination however must not collide with the IPR of the partners or with results that need to be protected (see Article 29 and 38 of the ECGA and article 8.4.2.1 of the CA for more information).

In this section we describe the mandatory rules for disseminating the results of the project and how to report the project outputs.

Dissemination strategy will be further complemented by deliverable D6.1 *Project dissemination and communication plan* and in *D1.2 Project Innovation strategy and DMP* both scheduled for M6.⁴

5.1. Acknowledgements

All the publications, conference proceedings, presentations on workshops, seminars, press releases, equipment, communications, patents, standard or public events must take into account the following obligation towards the EC (see article 29 and 38 of the ECGA):

5.1.1. Publications, conferences and events

Unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- (a) display the EU emblem and
- (b) include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761508”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Commission.

This does not however give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

(...)

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.⁵

5.1.2. Patents and standards

Application for protection of results (including patent applications) filled by or in behalf of a beneficiary must include the following:

⁴ More information at http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm.

⁵ Extract from article 29 ECGA

“The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761508”.

If results could reasonably be expected to contribute to European or international standards, the beneficiary concerned must inform the Commission (up to four years after the end of the project), and ask the standardisation body to include the following statement in (information related to) the standard:

“Results incorporated in this standard received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761508”.

5.1.3. Communications, major results, equipment

Any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must **inform the PC** and

(a) display the EU emblem and

(b) include the following text:

For communication activities:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761508”.

For infrastructure, equipment and major results:

“This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761508”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Commission.

(...)

Any communication activity related to the action must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

5.2. Reporting the outputs

All the outputs of the project (papers, proceedings, press releases, non-scientific publications...) and the dissemination actions (assistance to workshops, public demos, fairs...) have to be reported in a monthly basis to ensure a proper dissemination.

Despite of this periodic reporting, any relevant output, major result, equipment publicly displayed, patent or standard must be immediately informed.

The outputs of the project will be reported through an event tracking mechanism based on confluence. This event tracking mechanism will include the following sections:

1. Foreseen of assistance to events: In this section each partner will report the assistance to any event (congress, fair, workshop, demo...) and the objectives of the action.
2. Foreseen organization of events: In this section each partner will report the organization of any event related with the dissemination of the project and the foreseen objectives of the event.

3. Event reporting: In this section each partner will report the assistance to events. This report will include the date, place and name of the event, the members of the consortium that assisted, the audience profile and number of assistants, a short report of the results, any presentations or papers.
4. Publications reporting: The publications (book chapters, papers, proceedings, white paper or non-scientific and non-peer reviewed outputs) related with the project will be reported in this section. Each paper has to include the status (submitted, under review or accepted) and include the DOI. Other kind of publications has to include a link to the content.
As stated in CA the authors must inform the consortium of any foreseen publication at least 20 days in advance. Any objection must be done in writing within 10 calendar days after the receipt of the notice. If there is no objection the publication is permitted.

6. Abbreviations and Definitions

6.1. Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement.
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ECGA	Grant Agreement.
GA	General Assembly
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
MT	Management Support Team
PC	Project Coordinator
PMO	Project Management Office
PO	Project Officer
TB	Technical Board
TM	Technical Manager
IM	Innovation Manager
SMR	Six Month Report
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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